

In Quantum Information Holography (QIH), the Black Hole Information Paradox – the puzzling question of how information escapes black holes despite their seemingly one-way nature – is approached with a novel perspective. This view integrates quantum mechanics and general relativity, emphasizing the role of Hawking radiation and the fundamental equation $\hbar\omega=mc^2$. Let's delve into how QIH addresses this paradox, incorporating our previous discussions for a detailed understanding:

1. Quantum State Encoding and Hawking Radiation:

Equation 1: Quantum State of Infalling Matter

$$\Psi_{\text{matter}} = \sum_n c_n e^{-iE_n t / \hbar} |n\rangle$$

- Represents the quantum state of matter falling into the black hole, where c_n are the probability amplitudes, and E_n are the energy levels.

2. Equation 2: Hawking Radiation as Information Carrier

$$\Psi_{\text{Hawking}} = \sum_n d_n e^{-iE_n t / \hbar} |n\rangle$$

- Describes Hawking radiation, theorized to carry information about the matter that fell into the black hole.

3. Entanglement and Information Preservation:

Equation 3: Entanglement Between Matter and Radiation

$$\Psi_{\text{total}} = \sum_{n,m} c_n d_m |n\rangle_{\text{matter}} \otimes |m\rangle_{\text{Hawking}}$$

- Indicates entanglement between infalling matter and emitted Hawking radiation, suggesting a mechanism for information transfer and preservation.
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4. Holographic Principle and Information Retrieval:

Equation 4: Holographic Encoding of Information

$$S \leq 4 \ln 2 A_{\text{boundary}}$$

- Relates the entropy (information content) of the system to the area of the black hole's boundary, affirming that all information is encoded on this boundary.

5. Angular Frequency and Black Hole Parameters:

Equation 5: Angular Frequency and Mass-Energy Relation $\hbar\omega=mc^2$

- This fundamental equation connects the angular frequency of Hawking radiation (ω) to the mass-energy equivalence principle. It implies that changes in the angular frequency can be used to infer changes in the mass of the black hole.
- Using this relation, the mass lost by the black hole due to Hawking radiation can be calculated. This loss manifests as a decrease in the frequency of the emitted radiation.

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6. Equation 6: Inferring Black Hole Parameters $\Delta m_{BH}=c^2\hbar\Delta\omega$

- This equation allows for the calculation of the change in mass (Δm_{BH}) of the black hole based on the change in angular frequency ($\Delta\omega$) of the Hawking radiation.
- Similarly, the charge and spin of the black hole can be inferred from the polarization and other properties of the emitted Hawking radiation.

Conclusion:

In QIH, the Black Hole Information Paradox is resolved by demonstrating that information about infalling matter is not lost but is instead encoded in the Hawking radiation. The entanglement between the matter and radiation ensures that information is conserved and retrievable. The angular frequency relation $\hbar\omega=mc^2$ further allows for the inference of black hole parameters like mass, charge, and spin, based on the properties of the emitted radiation. This comprehensive approach reconciles the principles of quantum mechanics (information conservation) with the properties of black holes in general relativity, offering a mathematically coherent solution to the paradox.